

LEXICAL SEMANTIC ACTIVITIES AND THE WRITING PROFICIENCY IN PRACTICAL RESEARCH

LARIEL T. MANIMTIM

15-fs-eng-165@lspu.edu.ph

0000-0002-0724-6172

Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus
Brgy. Del Remedio (Wawa), San Pablo City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study utilized an experimental research design to determine if there was a significant difference in the writing proficiency of the students before and after the incorporation of the lexical semantic activities in the intervention classes done in the context of the subject, Practical Research. Writing tasks, in form of poem interpretation, picture analysis, and essay writing, served as the instruments of this study which was administered as pretest and posttest. This research purposively selected 30 samples from the Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences students from Talisay Senior High School who have access to internet and those who belonged to the above average, average, and below average levels in their respective classes. All the data gained in this research were subjected to data management and analysis through Mean, Standard Deviation, and T Dependent Test. According to the results of the analysis and statistical calculation, findings indicated the following difference in scores of the respondents writing proficiency in terms of organization and focus ($t=-6.420$), sentence structure ($t=-9.00$), language use ($t=-7.818$), and mechanics ($t=-9.021$), all with the p value < 0.05 . Thus, it can be concluded that, the null hypothesis stating that there was no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents in their writing proficiency before and after using lexical semantic activities was rejected. In view of the findings acquired in the study, teachers must devise diversified activities and teaching methods and develop a more effective approach on error analysis and recognition. Students must pay more attention in the cultivation of their writing skills. School administration provides programs that would cater the needs of the teachers in terms of error recognition and analysis.

Keywords: Practical Research, Writing Proficiency, Lexical Semantic Activities, Intervention Classes, Philippines